

INTRODUCTION

Business process management in conditions of high uncertainty caused by the increasing complexity of foreign economic relations requires developing methodological and applied approaches that contribute to an objective assessment of organizational activities effectiveness. The KPI (Key Performance Indicators) system is an analytical tool that allows for a multifaceted analysis, substantiates strategic development directions, and strengthens organizations' competitive positions [1; 2].

Methods based solely on aggregated financial and economic indicators demonstrate insufficient information content when analyzing complex interrelations of business processes. Their limitations are inability to consider the complex influence of internal and external factors, contributing to adopting suboptimal management decisions. The KPI system has the potential to eliminate these limitations by conducting a more in-depth key parameters analysis of the organization's functioning, covering economic, production, technological, and organizational components [3; 4]. This approach allows identifying structural imbalances, predicting the consequences of decisions, and developing sound strategies to achieve set goals.

The effectiveness of an organization's management requires integrative analysis algorithms based on KPI data. Significant tasks include identifying critical points that require optimization and implementing measures to streamline processes and minimize risks. Using scientifically based KPI analysis enhances the quality of management decisions and increases the compliance of adopted strategies with changing market conditions.

The article aims to develop algorithms for managerial decision-making based on a comprehensive analysis of the KPI system, including mathematical modeling and statistical data processing. This approach aims to increase organizations' adaptability and ability to function effectively in the context of digital transformation.

Special attention is paid to the conceptual understanding of the role of KPIs in management. The KPI system is considered a means of integrating quantitative and qualitative assessment methods, creating opportunities for forming a management concept that meets the requirements of a highly variable external environment.

Literature review

Scientific sources demonstrate the relevance of studying the methodological foundations of the KPI system in strategic and operational management, as well as in business transformation. A. A. Zaitsev and N. D. Dmitriev [2] reveal the methodological aspects of using the KPI matrix to evaluate the effectiveness of projects, focusing on identifying critical management areas and

improving the effectiveness of strategic decisions through an analytical approach. A study by A.V. Kubarsky et al. [4] is devoted to the analysis of applying the KPI system in the agricultural sector, which shows the role of monitoring production in improving managerial effectiveness and rationalizing the use of resources, which is enhanced by digitalization of management models. E. N. Vakhrusheva et al. [5] consider creating analytical models to justify management decisions based on KPIs, confirming their applicability in complex production systems.

D. G. Rodionov et al. [6] focus on applying econometric modeling to diagnose sustainable development of industrial enterprises, with attention on building predictive models to analyze market instability. N. D. Dmitriev [7] explores approaches to assessing intellectual capital, including integrating intellectual resources into strategic management to strengthen the sustainability of economic entities. The author emphasizes the synergetic relationship between philosophical and economic potentials for developing promising management strategies.

In their research, K. Alam et al. [8] pay attention to digital competence as a tool for strategic planning and sustainable regional development, offering analytical models for assessing digital maturity. H. Amiri et al. [9] study the correlation between the quality of the institutional environment and production, identifying the need for institutional reforms to increase competitiveness in resource-dependent economies globally. S. Tuo and H. He [10] use oversized data analysis to study economic relationships between regions, emphasizing the promising role of machine learning in identifying economic patterns.

The analysis of sources demonstrates the increasing role of digital technologies in improving management effectiveness. The paper [11] reveals the theoretical aspects of economic systems digitalization, highlighting the importance of adapting management strategies to the challenges of the digital age. The study by A. A. Afanasyeva et al. [12] captures the growing demand for digital technologies in industry, revealing various digital transformation trends (local and global). The analysis [13] is devoted to studying competitive advantages achieved through intellectualization of business processes, which helps increase their adaptability in a highly dynamic environment.

Approaches to quality management in industry, based on analytical tools, are focused on improving the accuracy of control and efficiency of production. The study [14] outlines concepts that contribute to improving quality management using predictive models and analytical approaches. These methodological developments ensure sustainability of production, cost optimization, and risk reduction. Trofimova [15] examines the problems of adapting business processes to digital transformation, offering conceptual models focused on improving management systems in the context of intensifying technological changes.

Special attention in research is paid to synthesizing analytical tools with quality management, contributing to achieving optimal efficiency. The work by G. R. Bakiev and A. V. Bannov [16]

analyzes the methods of product and service quality management and assesses their impact on the financial performance of enterprises. The authors emphasize the importance of integrating statistical methods and modern technologies to improve the efficiency of production systems. A study by C. Bai and J. Sarkis [17] focuses on blockchain technologies and analytical systems for optimizing supply chains and improving sustainability in the context of the dynamics of the macroeconomic environment. This approach reflects digitalization and innovation as mechanisms for increasing the efficiency and adaptability of economic systems.

The analysis of modernization processes in the agricultural sector reveals the multidimensional nature of the problems associated with introducing innovative technologies into traditional production chains. A.V. Kubarsky et al. [18] explore barriers to digitalization and automation of agriculture, including limited available resources and insufficient infrastructure development. The work highlights the importance of innovative strategies to increase productivity and sustainability of agro-industrial complexes. A study by S. S. Kamble et al. [19] examines supply chain management in the agricultural sector, focusing on the possibilities of adapting analytical tools to improve management.

Forming an investment policy is a key task in economic management, aiming to rationalize resources allocation to improve effectiveness. A study by V. N. Khodyrevskaya and I. V. Pripadcheva [1] analyzes the correlation between investment strategies and the economic system, highlighting the importance of a systematic approach to resource assessment. Scientists focus on the potential of detailed investment planning as a tool for sustainable functioning of organizations in conditions of uncertainty and turbulence. Works devoted to investing in strategically essential resources reveal the principles to consider when deciding in an unstable economic environment.

Modernization of strategic management, considering the challenges of globalization and the transformation of technological paradigms, is regarded as a key task of modern research. In [20], the issues of sustainable economic growth are analyzed, emphasizing the need for strategic analysis and for the application of innovative technological solutions in management practice. Integrating digital technologies with strategic management systems is seen as a catalyst for enterprises' adaptability and increased flexibility. The evolution of strategic approaches to economic realities lays the foundations for long-term stability and effective functioning of organizations.

Several studies consider application of performance indicators in various fields: in freight transportation [21], in autonomous marine vessels [22], in environmental protection [23], in agriculture [24], fisheries [25], healthcare [26], education [27], business and innovation [28].

P. C. Abeyesiriwardana and U.K. Jayasinghe-Mudalige proposed a single window performance management system model that provides high-level data exchange in a compatible manner

and facilitates data-driven decisionmaking. The proposed model describes in detail the key performance indicators that are compared with key performance drivers and appropriate policy measures to restructure these practices to create a results-based research culture that promotes appropriate scientific assessments [29].

P. Raval et al. determine and evaluate KPIs related to the use of blockchain technology in construction projects, using a multi-criteria decision-making tool such as the Analytic Network Process (ANP) [30].

B. Verhaelen et al. present a KPIs network for global production networks that links key site-level and enterprise-level indicators. This KPI network is integrated into the Performance Measurement and Management (PMM) methodology which consists of three stages: efficiency planning, efficiency improvement, and efficiency analysis [31].

H. Franzon and L. M. Rose develop KPIs related to work environment deviations such as risk observations, dangerous situations, and injuries. This is how managers support decision-making when managing companies, promoting higher risk awareness and the development of safer and more sustainable work environments and workplaces [32].

According to G. Karnitis et al., KPIs and their weighting coefficients are still largely determined subjectively, and there are no qualitative and quantitative justifications for the choice. The authors describe a universal methodology developed for objective mathematical calculation of KPIs processes and determination of their weighting coefficients [33].

These studies reveal the relevance of applying integrative approaches to quality management, resource allocation, and strategic development. Synthesis of analytical methods, digital technologies, and predictive planning contributes to improving the efficiency of production systems in various economic sectors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The use of the KPI system in managing operational and strategic processes is conditioned by the need to introduce highly adaptive analytical tools to assess efficiency objectively and informed decision-making in conditions of highly variable external factors. The KPI system acts as an integrative platform based on quantitative and qualitative indicators that diagnose productivity and effectiveness at all levels of the organizational structure. In the context of strategic planning, it promotes a comprehensive understanding of the internal dynamics of processes and creates the basis for building adaptive management models.

Traditional approaches to performance assessment are often limited to financial indicators and do not fully reflect the multifactorial interactions typical of complex organizational systems.

This approach makes it impossible to consider the peculiarities and interdependencies of various resources. In contrast, the KPI system allows for a diverse analytical profile, including production, technological, human, and innovative resources.

Developing decision-making algorithms based on the KPI system involves consistent data analysis which includes the following steps:

- Data collection including integrating information from various sources across multiple indicators, such as productivity, costs, product or service quality, customer satisfaction, and other critical indicators.
- Normalization and weighting of data to unify metrics and ensure their comparability. For normalization, linear transformation and calculation of standard deviations are used to minimize the impact of unit heterogeneity.

Integrating the KPI system with mathematical modeling algorithms contributes to developing techniques to identify priority areas for optimizing management. An example of this approach is using a formula for calculating an integral performance indicator, where weighted KPIs are summed up. The specified formula is:

$$K_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot KPI_i \quad (1),$$

Where K_{total} is the integral performance indicator, w_i is the weighting factor characterizing the relative importance of each indicator, KPI_i is the value of the performance indicator, and n is the total number of analyzed indicators.

Applying this methodology in strategic management allows for highly adaptable management solutions. Mathematical analysis and statistical modeling used to evaluate the effectiveness the KPI system include tools such as correlation and regression analysis, which enable identification of complex interdependencies between indicators. Applying these approaches lays the foundation for forming integrative solutions that enhance organizations' effectiveness in a dynamically changing external environment.

Quantitative assessment, which uses an integrated approach, completes the formation of solutions based on the KPI analysis. This approach, based on the concepts of system analysis, allows identifying areas for transformation and performance improvement at all levels of the organizational structure.

When calculating KPIs, considering the wide range of methods used, it is reasonable to use a multi-criteria approach that considers the multiplicity of factors affecting productivity and efficiency. The formula developed for calculating the integral indicator reflects an integrated approach, which considers the weighting factors for each indicator, as well as additional parameters such as economic conditions, resource intensity of processes, and uncertainties.

The generalized formula is:

$$K_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot KPI_i + \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_j \cdot Z_j + \alpha \cdot Risk_{factor}, \quad (2)$$

Where K_{total} is an integral performance indicator based on KPIs; KPI_i is the value of the i -th performance indicator (for example, productivity, quality, costs); w_i is the weighting factor for the i -th indicator, taking into account its relative importance; n is the number of KPIs selected for analysis; Z_j are additional parameters or indicators such as external factors (economic or market conditions); λ_j is the weighting factor for the j -th additional indicator; m is the number of additional factors influencing decision-making; α is the coefficient regulating the impact of risk; $Risk_{factor}$ is the risk variable calculated using statistical analysis methods.

Possible deviations from the average values and their effect on the integral indicator are to be considered to improve the model's accuracy. For instance, it is possible to include correction factors that reflect external environment instability or KPIs volatility. Such adjustments are justified in situations with high variability of market conditions, which allows predicting the consequences of management decisions more adequately.

Including risk factors and variability helps develop a more flexible management strategy. The correlation between indicators and external conditions is usually revealed using regression analysis, which forms the basis for building analytical forecasts. The developed formula of the integral performance indicator serves as a tool for solving problems related to multi-criteria optimization, in which the complex dynamics of economic processes must be taken into account.

Evaluating the relationships between performance indicators using correlation and regression methods helps identify hidden patterns and develop management solutions. Correlation analysis provides a quantitative description of interdependence between different indicators, which allows determining how changes in one of the parameters (for example, costs) affect others (for example, profit indicators). The correlation formula shown below is used to calculate the coupling coefficient:

$$\rho_{KPI_1, KPI_2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (KPI_{1i} - \overline{KPI_1})(KPI_{2i} - \overline{KPI_2})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (KPI_{1i} - \overline{KPI_1})^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (KPI_{2i} - \overline{KPI_2})^2}}$$

Correlation analysis is used to identify the direction and strength of the relationships between the indicators, which allows identifying the main dependencies in the managed system.

Regression models are used to predict the values of performance indicators, taking into account exogenous factors. Multivariate regression models the relationship between independent variables such as economic, social, and technological parameters and KPIs:

$$KPI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon$$

Where KPI_t is the KPI value at time t ; X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n are independent variables (costs, time, innovative resources); $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ are regression coefficients; ϵ is the accidental error.

This model allows us to consider multidimensional factors affecting organizational processes and predict changes depending on the external environment dynamics. Regression coefficients reflect the influence of each variable on the target indicator, and random error models the stochastic nature of unforeseen factors.

RESULTS

The research conducted included developing an algorithmic approach to integrating the KPI system with mathematical modeling methods to assess the effectiveness dynamics of management decisions in an unstable environment. The analysis covered production, financial and technological parameters reflecting the multidimensional nature of the organization's activities.

As part of the analytical work, indicators that characterize productivity, costs, quality, and customer satisfaction were selected. Based on the data obtained, an integral efficiency indicator is calculated, taking into account the relative weighting coefficients of KPIs and external parameters such as market conditions and resource availability. Formation of the integral index was based on modeling, which assumes that the influence of environmental instability through the risk factor is considered.

The dynamics of key indicators for the analyzed period demonstrate a steady positive trend:

- Performance (KPI_1): 85.4 → 97.1 in 2018-2022.
- Costs (KPI_2): 120 → 105 in 2018-2022.
- Quality (KPI_3): 78.5 → 82.4 in 2018-2022.
- Customer Satisfaction (KPI_4): 82.1 → 89.0 in 2018-2022.
- Market conditions (Z_1): -5% → +3% in 2018-2022.
- Resource availability (Z_2): -3% → +2% in 2018-2022.
- Riskfactor: considers the external environment's instability, 1.05 → 1.15.

The KPI integration algorithm took into account the influence of the external environment by applying weighting coefficients for each parameter (for example, $w_1=0.3$, $w_2=0.2$, $w_3=0.2$, $w_4=0.3$) and risk coefficients ($\lambda_1=0.25$, $\lambda_2=0.25$, $\alpha=0.5$). An integrated approach demonstrated that a rational combination of internal and external factors affects the quality of decisions and ensures adaptability. The calculation results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Dynamics of the integral indicator of management efficiency

Year	KPI ₁	KPI ₂	KPI ₃	KPI ₄	Z ₁	Z ₂	Risk _{factor}	K _{total}
2018	85.4	120	78.5	82.1	-5%	-3%	1.10	0.746
2019	91.7	118	80.2	85.3	-2%	-1%	1.08	0.757
2020	88.2	125	79.4	84.0	0%	0%	1.05	0.749
2021	94.5	110	81.0	86.7	+1%	+1%	1.07	0.763
2022	97.1	105	82.4	89.0	+3%	+2%	1.15	0.785

The results demonstrate a steady improvement in management performance indicators, confirming the high level of organizational structures' adaptation to changes in the macroeconomic environment. The Integrated Efficiency Index (K_{total}), calculated considering the KPI system and the influence of external factors, increased from 0.746 in 2018 to 0.785 in 2022 (indicating positive dynamics and the ability of the management system to respond to fluctuations in external conditions).

Special attention was paid to analyzing the influence of exogenous variables on the final results. The dynamics of market conditions (Z₁) and resource availability (Z₂) demonstrated that, despite the initial negative impact of the external environment in 2018 (-5% and -3%, respectively), improvements (+3% and +2%, respectively) were observed in subsequent years to 2022 (indicating gradual adaptation and overcoming of external barriers).

The analysis included a study of the risk factor impact, ranging from 1.05 to 1.15 in the analyzed period. The increase in the indicator in 2022 (1.15) illustrates the growing uncertainty of the external environment. Nevertheless, the KPI system demonstrated resilience and the ability to offset the negative impact of risks.

The correlation method was used for in-depth analysis of the relationships between variables. For instance, a study of the relationship between market conditions (Z₁) and productivity (KPI₁) revealed a positive correlation with the coefficient $\rho(\text{KPI}_1, Z_1) = 0.85$ (which confirms that favorable market changes have a positive effect on production performance). The correlation analysis is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Correlation analysis results

Parameters	Correlation coefficient (p)
Productivity and market conditions (KPI ₁ , Z ₁)	0.85
Costs and market conditions (KPI ₂ , Z ₁)	-0.42
Quality and availability of resources (KPI ₃ , Z ₂)	0.76
Customer Satisfaction and Risks (KPI ₄ , Risk _{factor})	-0.38

Correlation analysis confirms high dependence of production performance and product quality on market conditions and resource availability. On the contrary, costs and customer satisfaction showed a moderately negative correlation with market changes and risks (indicating their sensitivity to fluctuations in the external environment).

A regression model (Table 3) was used to predict the KPI values, which allows us to assess the impact of exogenous factors on KPIs. Regression analysis revealed that key indicators such as quality (KPI₃) have a linear dependence on market conditions and resource availability (confirmed by the high statistical significance of the model).

Table 3

Regression analysis results

Parameter	Regression coefficients (β)
Productivity and market conditions (KPI ₁ , Z ₁)	$\beta_1 = 1.32$
Costs and market conditions (KPI ₂ , Z ₁)	$\beta_2 = -0.82$
Quality and availability of resources (KPI ₃ , Z ₂)	$\beta_3 = 0.45$
Customer satisfaction and risks (KPI ₄ , Risk _{factor})	$\beta_4 = -0.15$

The conducted research confirmed the effectiveness of using the KPI system to make managerial decisions under the influence of changing external factors. The developed framework, based on the synthesis of KPIs, external variables, and risk factors, demonstrated a high degree of adaptability of the organization. Analytical methods such as correlation and regression proved to be effective in strategic planning and formation of sustainable solutions.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Using the KPI system in business process management revealed increased objectivity of assessing management decisions effectiveness due to the integration of internal and external factors, including market parameters and resource availability. Using mathematical methods in analysis algorithms allows increasing the validity of decisions.

The results of the study reveal that using the integral performance indicator (K_{total}) creates the basis for a multidimensional analysis of the organization's activities. The methodology, which takes into account the interrelationships between multiple KPIs and exogenous variables, is effective in increasing the sustainability and adaptability of organizations.

The analysis of the interrelationships between production and economic indicators with external parameters using correlation and regression revealed statistical dependencies. The high correlations between productivity and market conditions, as well as the quality and

availability of resources, emphasize the priority of these factors in strategic management. Regression analysis revealed functional dependencies that form the basis for predicting the dynamics of KPIs and adjusting management strategies.

The methodology, based on a multi-criteria approach to calculating KPIs, integrating statistical models and using data analysis algorithms, is proposed to improve management decisions' effectiveness. A systematic approach to analysis allows us to identify areas for optimization, contributing to the development of long-term strategies for strengthening competitive positions and the stable development of organizations in the face of market turbulence.

Further development opportunities include machine learning and big data analysis techniques to create predictive models that can account for complex relationships between economic, organizational, and technological factors. Predictive models can significantly expand analytical potential by providing tools for developing adaptive strategies to manage changes in the digital economy and effectively respond to environmental challenges.

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